

QUANTITATIVE AND INFORMATIONAL ANALYSIS IN THE ASSESSMENT OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

Ruziev Abdumalik Artigalievich

Tashkent International University of Financial
Management and Technologies, Ph.D., Assoc. Prof.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15425442>

In conditions where digital technologies are penetrating deeper into all aspects of the economy and public life, digitalization is becoming a key trend in the development of the global economy, changing its structure and transferring it to a new qualitative state. Economic growth is increasingly based on technology and knowledge, turning them into the main productive forces. Thus, the digital economy and its achievements will become the main source of ensuring the well-being of the subjects of the global economy in the future.

It is worth noting that we live in a global knowledge economy, where the future belongs only to those who are able to turn knowledge and scientific discoveries into products. Innovation, adaptation and use of new technologies are key factors in the growth of both national and global economies.

An analysis of individual groups of digital economy development indicators considered in international digital economy development ratings shows that the assessment of the development of the country's telecommunications infrastructure is taken into account in all indices. The level of the institutional base and innovation environment (political and business environment that stimulates digitalization processes), population access to information and communication services, and the level of knowledge and practical skills in using ICT are assessed. The areas of Internet use by the population and the application of digital technologies in business, the development of the ICT sector, the impact of ICT on the economy and society, as well as the consequences arising from the development of leading digital technologies are analyzed.

As a result of the analysis of existing international indices, it can be concluded that the presented index indicators have a number of unique features in the structure of their components and the number of main groups and subgroups, as well as the calculation method. At the same time, all indices reflect aspects related to the development of the digital economy. At the same time, all of them, to one degree or another (non-systematic), take into account the development of information and telecommunication technologies. Thus, on the one hand, there is a correlation between these indices, but on the other hand, they demonstrate different approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "digitalization".

It follows from the above that, despite the current rapid development of the digital economy, there are a number of problems associated with its definition, classification and measurement. The existence of definitions that do not clearly distinguish between the traditional and digital economies essentially leads to difficulties in comparing and analyzing the digital economy, as well as in assessing its development. In particular, if the digital economy is defined solely on the basis of the technologies used in companies, it may not take into account the digital technologies that cover a large part of the national economy [6]. Naturally, the lack of a generally accepted definition of the digital economy or digital sector, as well as the lack of classification of economic sectors and products for Internet platforms and related services, makes it difficult to fully assess the digital economy. Given the growth in the number of economic activities carried out using digital technologies and, as a result, their growing economic importance, measuring the digital economy is a key issue.

An analysis of existing international indices and rating indicators, their micro-indices, sub-indices and methods for forming composite indices, their advantages and disadvantages, common features and differences will allow them to be used in the future to form new authorship indices reflecting the level of countries' readiness for the digital economy and the level of digital globalization.

Digital technologies and information processes directly influence various definitions of the digital economy. The most important point here is that the criteria for assessing the development of the digital economy are determined based on the level of validity of the concept.

The need to develop these criteria is due to the fact that they determine the efficiency of using economic resources. The reason for this is that there are national indices of digital economy development and international indices of digital economy development, which are developed on the basis of different principles.

These principles determine how effectively economic resources are used. It is worth noting that economic resources are distributed differently in different countries and regions, which in turn raises the question of correctly defining the criteria for assessing the development of the digital economy.

For this purpose, we propose the following scheme for considering the general methodological essence and practical aspects of the concept of the "Index of Economic Functionality of Information in the Digitalization of

Information Resources” (IEFIDIR), which was first introduced into the theory and practice of digitalization of the economy (Fig. 1).

Considering that the totality (availability) of economic resources of the national economy is the basis of any economic process and social relations, we represent them in the form of labor, natural, information and capital resources.

As can be seen from this diagram, the elements are presented, representing the main logically inseparable level of this index. If we consider IEFIDIR as a systematized category, then the solution to the problem of implementing the "Potential value of information" is the basis of this systematized category.

At the same time, it is worth emphasizing that the existence of such potential value is objective; the whole problem lies in the awareness of this objectivity. For this purpose, the position and significance of digitalized information are expressed through its connection with other information by means of direct and inverse connections.

Figure 1. Economic efficiency index (IEFIDIR) in the digitalization of information resources

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that today a fairly extensive apparatus for assessing the level of development of the digital economy has been formed using various international composite indices. At the same time, international methods for assessing the development of the digital economy are also not without drawbacks, since they mainly involve assessing the level of ICT infrastructure and the involvement of the population in the Internet. In this regard, there is a need to develop an index of digital economy development, which will identify problem areas in the digitalization process in the Republic of Uzbekistan, eliminate existing problems and thereby improve its position in various world digital ratings. In conclusion, it should be noted that the digitalization of the economy should be considered as a key factor determining the level of development of the innovative economy. This indicates the advisability of conducting a comprehensive study of the methodological aspects of assessing the level of digital and innovative development of economic systems. Further, it is important to conduct a detailed study of the recommended indicators for assessing digitalization and innovative development, as well as research to improve organizational assessment procedures.

Literature:

1. Bukht R., Heeks R. Defining, Conceptualising and Measuring the Digital Economy // International Organisations Research Journal. – 2018.
2. Maskus, K. Private Rights and Public Problems : The Global Economics of Intellectual Property in the 21st Century / K. Maskus. - Peterson Inst. for Intern. Economics, 2012. - P. 1.
3. Measuring the Digital Economy: A New Perspective. – Paris : OECD Publishing, 2014.
4. Measuring the Digital Economy. www.imf.org/en/Publications/Policy-Papers/Issues/2018/04/03/022818-measuring-the-digital-economy.
5. Ruziev A.A. Digital transformation as an object of studying relations in socio-economic development. Scientific Journal of “International Finance & Accounting” Issue 3, June 2022. ISSN: 2181-1016.
6. Ruziev A.A. International practice for assessing digitalization in the development of innovative economy. -№ 4 (3)-2023. ISSN: 2181-1342. <https://scienceproblems.u> 60-74 б.

7. WEF Expanding Participation and Boosting Growth: The Infrastructure Needs of the Digital Economy, Geneva, 2015. Available at: www3.weforum.org/docs/WEFUSA_DigitalInfrastructure_Report2015.pdf

